

LIFE SATISFACTION IN THE CAREGIVERS OF SCHIZOPHRENIA AND FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH IT: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY FROM SOUTH INDIA

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Abstract

Schizophrenia is a mental disorder characterized by distortions of thinking and perception, in the process of care giving the caregivers are faced with many challenges. These challenges have a significant impact on the life satisfaction of caregivers. The study investigates various factors associate with life satisfaction in caregivers of schizophrenia

The aim: 1. To evaluate the socio-demographic correlates associated with life satisfaction in the care givers of schizophrenia.

2. To evaluate the association between life satisfaction with resilience, anxiety, stress, depression perceived social support, self-esteem, self-efficacy, and perceived stigma in the care takers of schizophrenia patients.

Material and methods. In cross sectional study, 513 care takers of schizophrenia were evaluated using semi-structured socio demographic perfoma, DASS-21, Connor-Davidson Resilience 25 item scale, Self Esteem Scale (Rosenberg), The Satisfaction with Life Questionnaire and family stigma stress scale.

Result. The study showed that background of the caregiver, socioeconomic status, family type, education and marital status are significantly positive correlated with life satisfaction. The study also showed significant positive correlation between resilience, perceived social support, self-esteem and self-efficacy with life satisfaction. There is also significant negative correlation between perceived stigma, anxiety stress and depression with life satisfaction.

Conclusion. The study showed that life satisfaction in the care givers of schizophrenia depends on different biopsychosocial variables. There is strong positive correlation between self-esteem, other person support and resilience with life satisfaction, whereas there is moderate positive correlation between self-efficacy, family support and friend support with life satisfaction. There is significant negative correlation between stress, anxiety, depression, and stigma with life satisfaction. We recommended psycho educational interventional programmes in the community level which help to increase resilience self-esteem and self-efficacy. Such programmes also decrease the stigma which in turn increases the social support to the caregivers.

Keywords: care takers, life satisfaction, resilience, social support, stigma.

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1. Introduction

Schizophrenia is a mental disorder characterized by distortions of thinking and perception. It occurs a different cluster of symptoms grouped as positive, negative, affective, and cognitive symptoms. These symptoms reduce person's capacity for social relationship, curtail employment opportunities and produce functional impairment. This cause dependency on family members or to seek institutional support for a long term. Since the main treatment settings of schizophrenia has shifted from institution to community the role of caregivers has increased immensely.

A caregiver is defined as a non-professional person in the community who has most involved with everyday care of the patient and would be likely to respond to any request for special

assistance at any time if request is made by the patient. It has shown that patients of schizophrenia living with family has significant improvement functionally and clinically following psychosis [1]. But, in the process of care giving the caregivers are faced with many challenges. Unpredictable course of the illness, poor insight, unpredictable aggression, stigma associated with the illness can all contribute to challenges, and these could have a toll on the psychological wellbeing of the caregivers.

Studies conducted previously have reported an increase in the incidence of depression, anxiety, and stress among caregivers of individuals with schizophrenia [2, 3]. Several studies done on general population shows that stress, anxiety, and depression were associated with lower levels of life satisfaction in the care givers.

Literature also shows many individuals maintain high levels of life satisfaction despite the increased stress level. Further research is required to find how stress perceived by the care takers affects their satisfaction with life. Resilience is defined as the ability to withstand a threatening and challenging situation. A study done on university students showed that resilience and life satisfaction are positively correlated [4]. Interpersonal relationships have long been associated with satisfaction with life. Man being a social animal requires relationship with others. This includes the relationship with other members of family as well as society.

The support from family as well as society help caregivers cope with the challenges, they face during care giving. The results of research on the relations between interpersonal contacts and life-satisfaction are not clear or complete. Researchers have shown that various types of social support are beneficial for health. Social support can be an important interpersonal relationships factor in shaping life- satisfaction. In rural areas of developing countries like India mental illness are often stigmatized. This led to socially isolating not only the patients but also their family member. Stigma perceived by the caregivers therefore can be one of the factors determining the life satisfaction of the caregivers.

According to Rosenberg, self-esteem is an affective evaluation to one's self-worth [5]. Self-esteem influences various domains of life and can be one of the important factors affecting the life satisfaction. According to Noonan et al low self-esteem has been described as an inability to find meaning in the care giving. Inability to find meaning in the life can natively affect the mental health of the individual which in turn can cause low satisfaction in life. Albert Bandura defined self-efficacy as perception and confidence of one's competency beliefs [6]. A study done by Kate et al showed significant association between self-esteem and positive aspect of care giving [7]. Concentration on positive aspects of care giving help individuals face challenges in caregiving more effectively and this can have a positive effect on psychological wellbeing of the caregivers. Meruzzi et al showed that self-efficacy is negatively to stress and burden in the caregivers of mentally ill patients [8]. This implicates that self-efficacy play an important role in wellbeing of the care takers and well as in the quality of care giving.

There are very few studies focusing on the life satisfaction in caregivers of schizophrenia patients. Since life satisfaction has a strong influence on the mental health extensive research is required to find the factor associated with life satisfaction Therefore this study intend to evaluate the life satisfaction and factor associated with it in caregivers of the schizophrenia patients.

The aims of the research. 1. To evaluate the socio-demographic correlates associated with life satisfaction in the care givers of schizophrenia.

2. To evaluate the association between life satisfaction with resilience, anxiety, stress, depression perceived social support, self-esteem, self-efficacy, and perceived stigma in the care takers of schizophrenia patients.

2. Materials and methods

This is a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary hospital. Ethical consideration was taken from the institute MGM hospital Warangal. Informed consent was taken from all the participants. 513 caregivers of schizophrenia patients gave consent for the study. A semi-structured perfoma was used to collect the socio demographic data. The bioethics committee approval was taken (ECR/1278/INST/AP-45).

Scales

Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21 (DASS-21)

The DASS-21 (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995) is a short form of the DASS which is a self-report 4-point Likert scale that measures the negative states of three mental health conditions: depression, anxiety, and stress. The DASS-21 measures each of the three factors with a 7-item subscale that asks participants to reflect on the thoughts, feelings, and behaviour in the past week. Responses on each item are ranging from 0 (did not apply to me at all) to 3 (applied to me very much). The intensity of any of the three conditions is defined by the sum scores of responses to its 7-item subscale. According to Lovibond and Lovibond (1995), normal scores on the three subscales are scores that are less than 9 for Depression, 7 for Anxiety, and 14 for Stress.

Resilience

Resilience was measured with the Connor-Davidson Resilience 25 item scale. This is a self-report scale and consists of 25 items. Respondents rate the item on a scale of 0 to 4. The higher score reflects higher resilience. In the present study the score was calculated as follows: less than 50 % indicates mild level of resilience, score of 50–75 indicates moderate levels of resilience and score greater than 75 % indicates high resilience.

Self-esteem

Self-esteem was measured using Self Esteem Scale (Rosenberg) 2015. It consist of 10 items and response range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). The score range from 0 to 40. A score less than 15 suggest problematic low self-esteem. The scale has high reliability (cronbach's alpha 0.86).

Self-efficacy scale

The self-efficacy was measured using general self-efficacy scale. There are 10 items in the scale and he rated from 1 (not at all true) to 4 (strongly true). The score ranges from 10 to 40. Higher the score, higher the self-efficacy. The scale has good internal reliability (cronbach's alpha 0.76 to 0.80).

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support

The scale was developed by Zimet et al in 1988. The scale consists of a total of 12 items. Each item is rated in a 7-point Likert -type scale (1–7 points) ranging from no to absolutely yes. The scale has three sub scale to determine the support of family, friends, and special person. The lowest and highest scores obtained from the sub scales are 4 and 28 respectively. Total score is ranging from 12 to 84. Scale was tested for internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha values were 0.85, 0.88, 0.92 for the family sub scale, friend sub scale and other significant person sub scale respectively.

The Satisfaction with Life Questionnaire

The Satisfaction with Life Questionnaire was a combination of five items measured on a 5-point Likert scale. High scores on this measure also indicate greater life satisfaction [9].

Family stress and stigma questionnaire

Scale contains 8 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale. Higher the score, higher the perceived stigma.

Statistics and correlation Methods

SPSS 28.0 was used to analyse the data. Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney U Test (W) and Kruskal Wallis Test were used to evaluate the association between life satisfaction and other socio demographic variables. Spearman correlation was used to evaluate the correlation between various variables.

3. Result

The mean age of caregiver was 39.02 ± 12.97 .

The mean Duration of Caregiving (Years) was 6.90 ± 4.11 .

Majority of the caregivers were from rural background (67.4 %) and upper lower socio-economic status (42.7 %). Majority completed primary education (60.3 %) and married (60.8 %) (**Table 1**).

The mean Resilience was 41.02 ± 16.56 .

The mean Self Esteem was 15.86 ± 9.29 .

The mean Self Efficacy was 16.23 ± 9.53 .

The mean perceived stigma score was 15.49 ± 5.10 (**Table 2**).

Table 1
Summary of Clinical Details

Clinical details	Mean±SD Median (IQR) Min-Max Frequency (%)
Age (years)	32.96±8.24 31.00 (28.00–35.00) 19.00–63.00
Gender	
Male	284 (55.4 %)
Female	229 (44.6 %)
Background	
Rural	346 (67.4 %)
Urban	167 (32.6 %)
SES	
Lower	55 (10.7 %)
Upper Lower	219 (42.7 %)
Lower Middle	123 (24.0 %)
Upper Middle	108 (21.1 %)
Upper	8 (1.6 %)
Family	
Joint	216 (42.1 %)
Nuclear	297 (57.9 %)
Caregiver relation	
Parents	215 (41.9 %)
Spouse	167 (32.6 %)
Siblings	38 (7.4 %)
Children	32 (6.2 %)
Others	61 (11.9 %)
Age of caregiver	39.02±12.97 45.00 (26.00–46.00) 20.00–66.00
Duration of caregiving (years)	6.90±4.11 8.00 (2.00–10.00) 1.00–15.00
Education	
Primary	312 (60.8 %)
Middle School	173 (33.7 %)
High School	16 (3.1 %)
Graduate	12 (2.3 %)
Marital status	
Married	409 (79.7 %)
Single	7 (1.4 %)
Divorced	97 (18.9 %)

Table 2
Summary of scores

Scores	Mean±SD	Median (IQR)	Min–Max
Perceived stigma	15.49±5.10	17.00 (10.00–20.00)	8.0–25.0
Resilience	41.02±16.56	32.00 (27.00–65.00)	27.0–68.0
Self-Esteem	15.86±9.29	12.00 (9.00–24.00)	3.0–36.0
Self-Efficacy	16.23±9.53	12.00 (9.00–24.00)	3.0–36.0

The mean Family support was 33.78±18.53.

The mean Friend Support was 8.76±4.44.

The mean other person Support was 10.11±3.153 (**Table 3**).

Table 3
Summary of support

Support	Mean±SD	Median (IQR)	Min–Max
Other person support	10.11±3.15	10.00 (8.00–12.00)	5.0–17.0
Friend support	8.76±4.44	7.00 (6.00–12.00)	5.0–78.0
Family support	33.78±18.53	25.00 (19.00–50.00)	13.0–70.0

The highest support was from family whereas the lowest support was from friends. The mean Life Satisfaction was 15.00±8.83 (**Table 4**).

Table 4
Summary of outcome parameters

Outcome parameters	Mean±SD	Median (IQR)	Min–Max
Life satisfaction	15.00±8.83	11.00 (8.00–26.00)	5.0–31.0

Majority of the care givers had normal levels of stress, anxiety and depression (**Table 5**).

Table 5
Summary of Depression Anxiety Stress

Depression Anxiety Stress	Mean±SD	Median (IQR)	Min–Max
Anxiety	3.71±3.80	2.00 (0.00–6.00)	0.0–12.0
Depression	2.73±3.27	1.00 (0.00–6.00)	0.0–11.0
Stress	3.50±4.63	0.00 (0.00–8.00)	0.0–15.0

Table 6 shows that there is strong positive correlation between self-esteem, other person support and resilience with life satisfaction whereas there is moderate positive correlation between self-efficacy, family support and friend support with life satisfaction ($r = 0.5$, $p = <0.001$). There is significant negative correlation between stress, anxiety, depression, and stigma with life satisfaction.

Table 6
Correlation between life satisfaction and other variables

Correlation	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Self Esteem vs Life Satisfaction	0.6	<0.001***
Self-Efficacy vs Life Satisfaction	0.5	<0.001***
Family support vs Life Satisfaction	0.5	<0.001***
Friend Support vs Life Satisfaction	0.5	<0.001***
Other person Support vs Life Satisfaction	0.7	<0.001***
Stigma vs Life Satisfaction	-0.5	<0.001***
Anxiety vs Life Satisfaction	-0.7	<0.001***
Depression vs Life Satisfaction	-0.6	<0.001***
Stress vs Life Satisfaction	-0.4	<0.001***
Resilience vs Life Satisfaction	0.7	<0.001***

The association between the perceived support and life satisfaction showing significant positive correlation.

Table 7 shows there is significant positive association between background, socioeconomic status family type, education and marital status of caregivers with life satisfaction ($p < 0.001$).

There is significant negative correlation between duration of care giving and life satisfaction ($p < 0.001$).

Table 7
Association between life satisfaction and sociodemographic variables

Variable	Mean (SD)	Association
Gender	Male = 13.86 (8.09) Female = 16.41 (9.51)	Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney U Test (W) W = 29754.500, $p = 0.097$
Background	Rural = 13.64 (8.32) Urban = 17.81 (9.22) Lower = 17.00 (8.75) upper Lower = 15.62 (8.76)	W = 21222.000, $p = < 0.001^{***}$
Socio economic status	Lower Middle = 14.05 (8.41) Upper Middle = 12.80 (8.63) Upper = 28.75 (1.91)	Kruskal Wallis Test ($\chi^2 = 33.543$, $p = < 0.001^{***}$)
Family	Nuclear = 17.70 (9.40) Joint = 11.29 (6.34)	W = 20369.000, $p = < 0.001^{***}$

$< 0.05 = \text{significant association}^{***}$

Table 8 shows significant association between background, social economic status, family type, education and marital status.

There is significant negative correlation between duration of care giving and life satisfaction.

Table 8
Association between life satisfaction and parameters

Parameters	Life satisfaction	p value
Age (years)	Correlation coefficient (rho) = -0.05	0.268 ¹
Gender		0.097 ²
Male	13.86 ± 8.09	
Female	16.41 ± 9.51	
Background***		<0.001 ²
Rural	13.64 ± 8.32	
Urban	17.81 ± 9.22	
SES***		<0.001 ³
Lower	17.00 ± 8.75	
Upper Lower	15.62 ± 8.76	
Lower Middle	14.05 ± 8.41	
Upper Middle	12.80 ± 8.63	
Upper	28.75 ± 1.91	
Family***		<0.001 ²
Joint	11.29 ± 6.34	
Nuclear	17.70 ± 9.40	
Age of caregiver	Correlation Coefficient (rho) = 0.05	0.253 ¹
Duration of caregiving (Years)***	Correlation Coefficient (rho) = -0.58	<0.001 ¹
Education***		<0.001 ³
Primary	9.40 ± 3.29	
Middle School	25.96 ± 5.37	
High School	8.06 ± 1.91	
Graduate	11.83 ± 3.24	
Marital Status***		<0.001 ³
Married	12.05 ± 7.10	
Single	12.43 ± 3.78	
Divorced	27.64 ± 1.51	

4. Discussion

The study aimed to find out the factors associated with life satisfaction among care takers of schizophrenia. The study showed that background of the caregiver, socioeconomic status, family type, education and marital status are significantly positive correlated with life satisfaction. The study also showed significant positive correlation between resilience, perceived social support self-esteem and self-efficacy with life satisfaction. There is also significant negative correlation between perceived stigma, anxiety stress and depression with life satisfaction. A study done by Rocio et al in general population showed that education and income influence life satisfaction. This is in par with our study which also showed significant association between life satisfaction and income as well as education [10]. A study done by Arif Ali et al at investigating perceived social support and life satisfaction in people with somatization disorder, perceived social support showed a significant positive correlation with life satisfaction. This is like our study which also showed positive correlation between two [11]. A study done by Young et al in mentally ill patient showed significant association between friend's support and life satisfaction. In our study, it was shown that caregivers highest support the family, but low support from friends. This is mainly due to our culture and family system where family members are loving and supportive toward their loved ones and there exist a sense of commitment to support other members of the family whereas low perceived social support from friends can be due to the stigma associated with the illness. This also implies that more education should be given to the community about mental illness to reduce the stigma associated with the illness. The result is in par with the study done by Lok et al in 2011 [12], who found that the caregivers had moderate social support from family members.

A study done by Sahar Mahmoud in 2016 found that 56.6 % had low resilience, 30.9 % had moderate resilience and 23 % had good resilience [13]. These observed results could be due to use of a different instrument which measures collective resilience in the family whereas present study evaluated individual resilience. A study done by Neslishan et al in 2019 showed high resilience (88.15+/-11.62) in the caregivers. This difference can be attributed to the geographical difference as the study was conducted in European country where the standard of living and mental health care is higher than India. They also found that males and married caregivers have significantly high resilience, but such an association could not be found in our study [14]. According to Syamak et al, a study done in mentally ill patients showed. Resilience will lead to life satisfaction by means of reduced levels of negative emotions. Similar to this, our study shows significant positive correlation between resilience and life satisfaction in caregivers of schizophrenia [15]. Similar to present study. A study done by Stanley et al in-family caregivers of schizophrenia showed Significant statistical positive correlations for, resilience, and life satisfaction scores [16]. A study done by Atel Mokhtar et al in schizophrenia patients also showed significant association between resilience and life satisfaction. These results show that in spite of the participant group resilience has a significant correlation with life satisfaction [17]. Our study showed that there is significant negative association between stigma and life satisfaction in care takers of schizophrenia. A study done by Mathew in schizophrenia patients proved that there is significant correlation between Internalized Stigma of Mental Illness and Life Satisfaction of persons with Mental illness. A study done by Markowiitz F E in mentally ill patients also showed significant negative association between perceived [18].

Similar to our study Laurence et al in 2020 also reported that the social support from family was high compared to support from friends [19]. In our study it was showed that education, employment, and socioeconomic status had significant association with perceived social support. In par with the above study done by Neslishan et al in 2019, showed higher social support for educated caregivers. In contrast to our study, they also found that females have higher social support than male. This can be due the cultural differences existing across the continents, as the study was conducted in Europe where females have comparable social equality to males. A study done by Yeliz et al in 2022 showed moderate perceived social support (44.36+/-22.88). They also found that perceived supporters from family is the highest compared to support from friends and other significant person. This is in par with our study which also has similar result.

Self-esteem and self-efficacy in the caregivers of schizophrenia are grey areas of research and requires more research. The mean score of self-esteem was 20.22+/-3.4. In a study done by

Scholz et al in 2002, the international average of self-efficacy was found to be 29.55 which implies that care takers of our study had low self-efficacy [20]. In a study done by Durmaz et. al in 2014, the caregiver of schizophrenia has range of self-efficacy score was similar to our study [21]. They also found a negative correlation between self-efficacy and burden of caregivers. This implies that self-efficacy of the caregivers has a significant role in the quality of life of the caregiver. Similar to the above study a study done Ramzani et al in 2019, the mean of caregivers' self-efficacy score was 28.79 ± 5.60 . They also found that there is a significant negative correlation between caregiver burden and self-efficacy [22]. A study done by Kate et al in 2013 showed significant correlation between self-efficacy and positive care giving [23]. The above studies indicate that self-efficacy of the caregivers has significant importance in the quality of the care given by them. A caregiver high self-efficacy can effectively adapt to the challenges they face during care giving. In a study done by Zing et al in 2019, the mean self-esteem and self-efficacy score were 27.66 and 24.98 respectively, but this study was done in HIV patients on ART treatment. In par with our study, they also found that there is a positive correlation between resilience, perceived social support self-esteem and self-efficacy [24]. No research studies could be found focusing on the association between self-esteem, self-efficacy and life satisfaction in the caregivers of schizophrenia. Our studies showed a significant association between self-esteem and self-efficacy with life satisfaction in the caregivers of schizophrenia. In present student we found significant negative correlation between stress, anxiety, depression and life satisfaction in caregivers of schizophrenia.

A study by Mainz et al in showed that absence of anxiety and depression are of crucial importance for the maintenance of life satisfaction in ageing men. Similar to this study our study also showed significant correlation between anxiety, depression with life satisfaction. Headey et al on-life satisfaction as a dimensions of mental health documents that depression is a strong correlate of life satisfaction in the general population. Present study shows significant association between stress and life satisfaction in the caregivers of schizophrenia. A study done by Alleye et al in university students of Barbados showed that higher levels of perceived stress were associated with lower levels of satisfaction with life. Even though the study participants are different from our study, the results are similar.as both shows significant correlation perceived stress and life satisfaction.

Our study has certain **limitation**. This is a single centred study and generalisation of results requires further multi centred research. Since this is cross sectional study causal inferences cannot be made. Hence follow up studies are required.

Prospects for further research: The study showed the life satisfaction in care givers depends on various psychosocial factor. Very few studies have done in this area. Further multicentric studies should be carried out in order to find how culture influence the life satisfaction in the care givers. There should be further research on various interventions which can improve the psychological well-being and well as life satisfaction in the care givers.

5. Conclusion

1. The study showed that care takers have moderate resilience. They had received highest perceived social support from family and lowest support from friends. The study also showed that as the duration of care taking increase, the perceived social support, resilience self-esteem and self-efficacy of the care takers significant decreases. The study also found that resilience perceived social support self-esteem and efficacy has significantly positive correlation with life satisfaction of caregivers. Study also showed that perceives stigma, stress, anxiety, depression has significant negative correlation with life satisfaction of the caregivers.

2. We recommended psycho educational interventional programmes in the community level which help to increase resilience self-esteem and self-efficacy. Such programmes also decrease the stigma which in turn increases the social support to the caregivers.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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